

Description of two new non-planktotrophic species of *Haloceras* Dall, 1889 (Gastropoda, Haloceratidae) from the South Azorean Seamount Chain, with notes on other species assigned to this genus

Descripción de dos nuevas especies no planctotróficas de *Haloceras* Dall, 1889 (Gastropoda, Haloceratidae) de la cadena de montes submarinos del sur de las Azores, con notas sobre otras especies asignadas a este género

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ABSTRACT

Two new non-planktotrophic species tentatively placed in the genus *Haloceras* Dall, 1889 are described from Hyères seamount in the South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC), and are distinguished from *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018 and the Western Atlantic "*Solariella*" *tubulata* Dall, 1927. The holotype and two shells of the latter species are illustrated, the generic placement in the genus *Echinogurges* Quinn, 1979 is rebutted, and its placement in *Haloceras* is formally proposed. To support this, a lectotype is designated for *Trochus* (*Margarita*) *clavatus* Watson, 1879, the type species of *Echinogurges*. Notes are provided on the external morphology of *H. meteoricum*, and two possible additional species from Hyères and Irving seamounts are figured. The three to five species present on the southern part of SASC form a small endemic radiation, related to the Western Atlantic *H. tubulatum*, but a new genus is not introduced for them because a more global phylogenetic hypothesis is lacking for the family Haloceratidae.

RESUMEN

Se describen dos nuevas especies no planctotróficas del monte submarino Hyères en la cadena de montes submarinos del sur de las Azores (SASC), que se incluyen provisionalmente en el género *Haloceras* Dall, 1889, y se distinguen de *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018 y de "*Solariella*" *tubulata* Dall, 1927 del Atlántico occidental. Se ilustran el holotipo y dos conchas de esta última especie, se rechaza su inclusión en el género *Echinogurges* Quinn, 1979, y se propone formalmente su inclusión en *Haloceras*. En apoyo

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de ello, se designa el lectotipo de *Trochus (Margarita) clavatus* Watson, 1879, la especie tipo de *Echinogurges*. Se aportan notas sobre la morfología externa de *H. meteoricum*, y se ilustran dos posibles especies adicionales de los montes submarinos Hyères e Irving. Las tres o cinco especies presentes en la parte sur de la SASC forman una pequeña radiación endémica, relacionada con *H. tubulatum* del Atlántico occidental, pero no se introduce un nuevo género para ellas a falta de una hipótesis filogenética más global de la familia Haloceratidae.

KEYWORDS: Seamount endemism, Local radiation, Taxonomy, *Haloceras japonicum*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Endemismo de montes submarinos, Radiación local, Taxonomy, *Haloceras japonicum*.

INTRODUCTION

The South Azorean Seamount Chain (SASC hereafter) is located in the Central North Atlantic and comprises five main seamounts (Great Meteor, Irving, Atlantis, Hyères and Plato). Physiographic and oceanographic settings relevant for molluscan distributions and previous taxonomic studies on Mollusca in SASC have been summarized by CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* (2023) and will not be repeated here. These authors listed 439 species of molluscs from this area, but much of the studied material deserves further study. The purpose of this paper is to revise a group of SASC non-planktotrophic species in the family Haloceratidae, comprising the recently described *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018 (GOFAS, 2018) and two more species tentatively identified by CABALLERO-HERRERA *ET AL.* (2023) as the Western Atlantic *Haloceras tubulatum* (Dall, 1927), which are described here as new.

WARÉN & BOUCHET (1991) erected the family Haloceratidae for a group of rare deep-water gastropods, most of them from the Indo-Pacific realm and most of them with a protoconch morphology indicating a long-lived planktotrophic larva. There are currently 22 accepted species (20 extant and 2 extinct) in the family (MOLLUSCABASE, 2023). A recent phylogenetic study based on molecular data by TAKANO *ET AL.* (2022) suggested that Haloceratidae is a sister clade to Capulidae and that

both families form the superfamily Capuloidea.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material studied here was collected during Seamount 2 campaign organized by the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris (hereafter MNHN) and conducted in January/February 1993 by the first author on board the R/V "Le Suroit". The Great Meteor, Hyères, Irving, Plato, Atlantis and Tyro seamounts were sampled (69 dredge hauls and 16 beam trawl operations shallower than 1000 m, see GOFAS, 1993).

In the Seamount cruises and other MNHN surveys, the coarse fractions, usually above 10 mm, were mostly sorted on board to phyla, then sorted to species level in the lab. The finer fractions were preserved on board, and later sieved on 5, 2, 1 and 0.5 mm sieves, and sorted under a stereomicroscope. Most of the specimens and species are in the size range 1-5 mm, and the largest part consisted of shells only. The material from Seamount 2 is deposited in MNHN.

Abbreviations:

MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris.

NHM: Natural History Museum, London.

NMNH (USNM): National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Invertebrates collection.

SYSTEMATICS

Family HALOCERATIDAE Warén & Bouchet, 1991

Genus *Haloceras* Dall, 1899

Type species: *Cithna cingulata* Verrill, 1884, by monotypy. Grammatical gender: neuter as formed from the Greek word κέρας (given as example in ICZN Art. 30.1.2).

Haloceras meteoricum Gofas, 2018 (Figs. 1, 2)

Type material. *Holotype*: 1 shell (2.5 × 1.9 mm); Great Meteor seamount; 30.030°N, 28.368°W; 470 m; Seamount 2 sta. DW152, MNHN-IM-2000-34142. *Paratypes*: 10 shells; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-34143.

Other material examined: 96 shells from Great Meteor Seamount, 81 shells from Hyères Seamount and 4 shells from Irving Seamount (see GOFAS, 2018 for details). Not found on Atlantis seamount despite intensive sampling in the appropriate depth range.

Remarks: This species was described in detail by GOFAS (2018), but a plate is included here for comparison (Figure 1). A shipboard drawing of the living animal, overlooked in the original description, is included here, but the preserved specimen could not be located in MNHN collections. The animal (Figure 2) has an elongated foot, truncated anteriorly and leaf-shaped posteriorly, with propodium and metapodium separated by a deep dimple. Operculum present. Head relatively large, provided with cylindrical tentacles, with quite large eyes embedded at their base and slightly bulging. A large penis can be seen emerging at some distance behind the right cephalic tentacle.

The most similar Recent species to *Haloceras meteoricum* is *H. japonicum* Okutani, 1964, originally described from a holotype and a paratype from off Miyake Island (Izu Islands, Japan, 34.167°N, 140.092°E, 1230–1350 m (OKUTANI, 1964: 397–398, pl. 6, fig. 8). The holotype of *H. japonicum* was redescribed and illustrated by WARÉN & BOUCHET (1991: 143, fig. 62), and OKUTANI (2000: 205, pl. 102, fig. Haloceratidae 1). A third specimen from the eastern Pacific (off Oregon, 45°50'N, 125°14'W, 1580 m) was assigned to this species by WARÉN & BOUCHET (1991: figs. 64–65). It contained brooded embryos of a little more than 1 mm in

diameter (for an adult shell nearly 6 mm high), with a protoconch sculpture of quincuncially arranged tubercles like in *H. meteoricum*. Nevertheless, this characteristic protoconch could not be compared to that of the types of *H. japonicum* in which the protoconch is missing. HASEGAWA (2009) recorded a fourth (live collected) specimen assigned to this species, more than 600 km north of the type locality, off Iwate prefecture (39.557°N, 142.855°E to 39.560°N, 142.888°E, 1499–1480 m). This author described a distinctive thick periostracum in this specimen, which also appears hairy on his fig. 73C. Such periostracum is not observed in the holotype nor in the other reported specimen of *H. japonicum*, and not seen either in fresh shells of *H. meteoricum*. Nevertheless, WARÉN & BOUCHET (1991) described the type material of *H. japonicum* as having a thick, strongly adherent and dark greenish brown periostracum, which is evident in the holotype photographs in OKUTANI (2000: 205, pl. 102, fig. Haloceratidae 1). Although the figure by HASEGAWA (2009: fig. 73A–C) showed a shell with a more flattened spire and a sculpture which differs from the holotype of *H. japonicum*, this author consider that it agrees with previous described specimens in general shell characters. The protoconch seems to be well preserved in this specimen, but it was not described or illustrated.

Figure 1. *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018, from Great Meteor seamount, Seamount 2 sta. DW152 (30.030°N, 28.368°W, 470 m). A: holotype (MNHN-IM-2000-34142, 2.5 × 1.9 mm); B: protoconch of the holotype; C: apical view of a shell (1.5 mm diameter); D: apical view of another shell (1.4 mm diameter); E: protoconch, same shell as D; F: detail of sculpture of first whorl (framed area on D); G-I: shell (2.2 × 1.8 mm). A-F: SEM micrographs; G-I: light photographs.

Figura 1. *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018, del monte submarino Gran Meteor, estación Seamount 2 DW152 (30,030°N, 28,368°W, 470 m). A: holotipo (MNHN-IM-2000-34142, 2,5 × 1,9 mm): B: protoconcha del holotipo; C: vista apical de una concha (1,5 mm de diámetro); D: vista apical de otra concha (1,4 mm de diámetro); E: protoconcha de la misma concha que en D; F: detalle de la escultura de la primera vuelta (área enmarcada en D); G-I: concha (2,2 × 1,8 mm). A-F: microfotografías electrónicas de barrido; G-I: fotografías ópticas.

TAKANO ET AL. (2022, fig. 1) illustrated two species (*Haloceras* sp. 1 and *Haloceras* sp. 2) from Japan which share a paucispiral protoconch with *Haloceras japonicum* but have a more angular shoulder to the teleoconch whorls than

the latter species, and suggested their close phylogenetic relationship. These authors also pointed out that the specimen figured by HASEGAWA (2009) as *H. japonicum* has a thicker periostracum than the holotype of this species, and

Figure 2. *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018. Shipboard drawing of a living specimen from Great Meteor seamount, Seamount 2 sta. DW152 (shell ca. 2 mm high).

Figura 2. *Haloceras meteoricum* Gofas, 2018. Dibujo realizado a bordo de un espécimen vivo del monte submarino Gran Meteor, estación Seamount 2 DW152 (concha unos 2 mm de alto).

considered this specimen as conspecific with their *Haloceras* sp. 2 (a juvenile specimen of 1.1 teleoconch whorls), based on the geographic proximity of the sites from which both specimens were collected. TAKANO ET AL. (2022) also commented on that the unique

specimen from Oregon identified as *H. japonicum* by WARÉN & BOUCHET (1991) may be another undescribed species given the great distance between the Japanese and American localities (about 7200 km) and its supposed direct development, a view with which we agree.

Haloceras tubulatum (Dall, 1927) n. comb. (Fig. 3)

Solariella tubulata DALL, 1927: 130. – BOSS, ROSEWATER & RUHOFF (1968: 327).

Echinogurges tubulatus (Dall, 1927) – QUINN (1979: 22-23).

Type material. *Holotype*: UNITED STATES • 1 shell (3.6 × 3.1 mm; Fig. 3 A-C); “off Fernandina” (actually off Georgia); 30.975°N, 79.642°W [30°58′30″N, 79°38′30″W]; 536 m [294 fathoms]; 5 May 1886; “Albatross” sta. 2668, United States Fish Commission; USNM 108109.

Other material examined (only photographs, Fig. 3 D-E): UNITED STATES • 2 shells, mislabelled as “*Echinogurges tabulata* [sic]” from “1 lot” (no number of specimens is given in the NMNH database, but see remarks); “off Georgia”; 30.733°N, 79.433°W [30°44′00″N, 79°26′00″W]; 805 m [440 fathoms]; 1 Apr. 1886; “Albatross” sta. 2415, United States Fish Commission; USNM 108415.

Type material examined of *Trochus (Margarita) clavatus* Watson, 1879 (for comparison; only photographs studied): VIRGIN ISLANDS • 7 shells (formerly syntypes, now lectotype and paralectotypes); off Culebra Island; 18.641°N, 65.092°W [18°38′30″N, 65°05′30″W], 713 m [390 fathoms]; 25 Mar. 1873; “Challenger” sta. 24; NHM 1887.2.9.315-20.

Description (based on the holotype): Shell (Figure 3) small (3.5 × 3.0 mm in original description, 3.6 × 3.1 mm measured on the photograph of the holotype), solid, consisting of 1 1/4 proto-

conch and 2 to 2 3/4 teleoconch whorls. Protoconch 970 μm in diameter, without a distinct protoconch I and protoconch II, with a sculpture of closely set minute tubercles, about 20 of them across the

Figure 3. *Haloceras tubulatum* (Dall, 1927). A, B: holotype (USNM 108109, 3.5 × 3.0 mm) of *Solariella tubulata* Dall, 1927, “off Fernandina” (actually off Georgia), “Albatross” sta. 2668 (30.975°N, 79.642°W; 536 m); C: detail of protoconch and first teleoconch whorl in apical view; D, E: additional shells (USNM 108415), 3.6 × 3.0 mm, 2.6 × 2.3 mm, off Georgia, “Albatross” sta. 2415 (30.733°N, 79.433°W, 805 m). SEM micrographs (A-C) and light photographs (D, E) by Yolanda Villacampa, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution (<http://www.nmnh.si.edu/>).

Figura 3. *Haloceras tubulatum* (Dall, 1927). A, B: holotipo (USNM 108109, 3,5 × 3,0 mm) de *Solariella tubulata* Dall, 1927, “frente a Fernandina” (en realidad, frente a Georgia), “Albatross” estación 2668 (30,975°N, -79,642°W; 536 m); C: detalle de la protoconcha y de la primera vuelta de la teleoconcha en vista apical; D, E: conchas adicionales (USNM 108415), 3,6 × 3,0 mm, 2,6 × 2,3 mm, frente a Georgia, “Albatross” estación 2415 (30,733°N, 79,433°W, 805 m). Microfotografías de barrido (A-C) y ópticas (D, E) de Yolanda Villacampa, National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution (<http://www.nmnh.si.edu/>).

whorl height, aligned along two different oblique directions so as to form a quincuncial pattern. Protoconch/teleoconch discontinuity very sharp, slightly detached from the following whorl. Teleoconch whorls strongly carinate, shouldered, with a moderately deep suture. Sculpture consists of axial ribs and spiral keels forming a broad mesh, and fine prosocline growth lines. Axial ribs are not very prominent, irregular and much narrower than the interspaces, fading out abapically. Spiral sculpture of two strong keels, forming a

wide, square periphery, and a somewhat weaker one visible on the last whorl, just below the prolongation of the suture, and four cords on the umbilical area. Axial ribs form nodules as crossing the spiral keels. Umbilicus narrow and deep, sharply delimited by the last abapical spiral cord, inside with axial striae. Aperture irregularly rounded, slightly angulated by the spiral sculpture. Outer lip thin, simple, receding in its upper half. Parietal edge of aperture thin, appressed to the previous whorl, at an angle with the columellar edge

Figure 4. *Trochus (Margarita) clavatus* Watson, 1879, type species of the genus *Echinogurges* Quinn, 1979. A-D: four views of the lectotype here designated (NHM 1887.2.9.315-20, 4.0 × 3.2 mm), off Culebra Island, Virgin Islands, West Indies, “Challenger” sta. 24 (18.642°N, 65.092°W, 713 m [390 fathoms], 25/03/1873); E: illustration in WATSON (1886: pl. 5, fig. 8, scale bar “a” measures 4.7 mm in the original print and is to represent the natural size). Photographs by Kevin Webb, NHMUK Photographic Unit, Natural History Museum, London.

Figura 4. *Trochus (Margarita) clavatus* Watson, 1879, especie tipo del género *Echinogurges* Quinn, 1979. A-D: cuatro vistas del lectotipo aquí designado (NHM 1887.2.9.315-20, 4,0 × 3,2 mm), frente a la isla Culebra, Islas Vírgenes, Indias Occidentales, “Challenger” estación 24 (18,642°N, 65,092°W, 713 m [390 brazas], 25/03/1873); E: ilustración en WATSON (1886: lámina 5, fig. 8, la escala gráfica “a” mide 4,7 mm en la lámina original para representar el tamaño natural). Fotografías de Kevin Webb, Unidad Fotográfica NHMUK, Natural History Museum, Londres.

which thickens towards the base. Colour entirely white.

Remarks: QUINN (1979: 23, figs. 45-46) described and illustrated the holotype of *Solariella tubulata*, mentioned one more specimen (probably the “fragment off Fernandina” in the original description), and examined 7 specimens from “Albatross” sta. 2415 (USNM 108415), that may correspond to the lot of six specimens “off Georgia, mostly defective” in the original description. On the basis of the photographs of the three studied specimens, we consider them conspecific.

QUINN (1979) tentatively included this species in his new genus *Echinogurges* although acknowledging that “whether it really belongs here must await examination of soft parts”. The type species of *Echinogurges* designated by QUINN (1979) is *Trochus (Margarita) clavatus* Watson, 1879, but he did not illustrate nor describe the type material of this species housed at NHM. After the study of photographs of the 7 syntypes (NHM 1887.2.9.315-20), we designate here as the lectotype a syntype of 4.0 × 3.2 mm measured on

photographs (Figure 4), which fits with the original description (WATSON, 1879: 705-706) and the redescription and illustration by WATSON (1886: 82-83, pl. 5, fig. 8) in size (4.3×3.3 mm, 0.17×0.13 inches in the original description) and other shell characters. The lectotype of *Trochus* (*Margarita*) *clavatus* is a nacreous shell ("with a pearly lustre" in the original description), properly placed in subclass Vetigastropoda. The absence of nacre and the large protoconch in "*Echinogurges*" *tubulatus* indicates that the generic placement in *Echinogurges* is not warranted.

Conversely, the shell shape, protoconch and sculpture undoubtedly relate Dall's species *Solariella tubulata* with *Haloceras meteoricum*. The latter species,

however, is smaller, has convex whorls without obvious keels, and tubercles on the protoconch much coarser although of similar arrangement. The tentative identification as *Haloceras tubulatum* (Dall, 1927) of specimens from SASC by CABALLERO *ET AL.* (2023), which are here described as two new species, was misled by the description of the protoconch as "smooth" by DALL (1927) and QUINN (1979), and is refuted by the sculpture pattern on the protoconch observed in SEM micrograph of the holotype of *Solariella tubulata*. The new species described below differ from both *H. tubulatum* and *H. meteoricum* for having a smooth protoconch and other characters detailed under those species' entries.

Haloceras hoffmani n. sp. (Fig. 5)

ZooBank: urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:1A0AD9F0-2AF2-483C-AE1A-E52747B23AB6

Type material. *Holotype*: HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (4.6×3.5 mm); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW200; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38803. *Paratypes*: • 6 shells (largest 5.6×4.1 mm); same data as for holotype; MNHN IM-2000-38804.

Other material examined: HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 5 shells (largest 3.4×3.3 mm); 31.314°N, 28.559°W; 1370–1480 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW197 • 52 shells (largest 6.2×4.8 mm); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW200; dredge • 1 shell; 31.275°N, 28.718°W; 640 m; 19 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW202; dredge • 12 shells; 31.158°N, 28.725°W; 845–990 m; 19 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW203; dredge.

Etymology: The specific name honours Leon Hoffman (Senckenberg am Meer, Germany), in recognition of a fruitful collaboration in the study of molluscs from the North Atlantic seamounts.

Description: Shell small (up to 6.2×4.8 mm, holotype 4.5×3.4 mm), solid, consisting of $1\frac{1}{4}$ protoconch and up to $2\frac{3}{4}$ (holotype 2.7) teleoconch whorls. Protoconch $1140\ \mu\text{m}$ (holotype) to $1200\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, without a distinct protoconch I and protoconch II, nearly smooth. Protoconch/teleoconch discontinuity very sharp, protoconch terminating with a distinctly flaring lip. Teleoconch whorls strongly carinate, shouldered, with a moderately deep suture. Sculpture consists of axial growth lines, poorly defined axial undulations, and spiral keels. Spiral sculpture of one definite keel at the upper $\frac{1}{3}$ of whorls, another somewhat weaker one visible on the last whorl in prolongation of the su-

ture, and one very indistinct between the two latter. Umbilicus narrow and deep, sharply delimited by an angulation. Aperture irregularly rounded, slightly angulated by the spiral sculpture. Parietal edge of aperture thin, appressed to the previous whorl, at an angle with the columellar edge which thickens towards the base. Colour entirely white.

Remarks: This species is diagnosed by the quite large protoconch, well over 1 mm in diameter, and the smoothish surface between keels, irregularly undulated without forming distinct axial ribs. It differs from *H. tubulatum* in lacking any ornamentation on the protoconch, and lacking the distinct narrow ribs and spirals on the teleoconch.

Figure 5. *Haloceras hoffmani* n. sp., from Hyères seamount, Seamount 2 sta. DW200 (31.318°N, 28.600°W; 640 m). A: paratype (MNHN IM-2000-38804, 2.0 × 2.2 mm); B: protoconch of another paratype (MNHN IM-2000-38804, juvenile, 1.4 × 1.7 mm), in lateral view; C: apical view of another paratype (MNHN IM-2000-38804, diameter 2.1 mm); D: apical view, same as A; E: protoconch, same paratype; F: detail of sculpture of first whorl (framed area on D); G-I: Holotype (MNHN IM-2000-38803, 4.6 × 3.5 mm).

Figura 5. *Haloceras hoffmani* n. sp., del monte submarino Hyères, estación Seamount 2 DW200 (31,318°N, 28,600°W; 640 m). A: paratipo (MNHN IM-2000-38804, 2,0 × 2,2 mm); B: protoconcha de otro paratipo (MNHN IM-2000-38804, juvenil, 1,4 × 1,7 mm), en vista lateral; C: vista apical de otro paratipo (MNHN IM-2000-38804, diámetro 2,1 mm); D: vista apical, mismo que A; E: protoconcha, mismo que A; F: detalle de la escultura de la primera vuelta (área enmarcada en D); G-I: Holotipo (MNHN IM-2000-38803, 4,6 × 3,5 mm).

Haloceras freiwaldi n. sp. (Fig. 6)

ZooBank: urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:241BC375-E5DB-41FB-9E4D-DBBF0AC5AD2B

Type material. *Holotype*: HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (4.6 × 3.8 mm); 31.314°N, 28.559°W; 1370–1480 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW197; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38805. *Paratypes*: • 6 shells (largest 4.5 × 3.6 mm); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW200; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38806.

Other material examined: HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 31.310°N, 28.585°W; 1240 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW198; dredge • 32 shells (largest 4.5 × 3.4 mm); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW200; dredge. • IRVING SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 32.025°N, 27.908°W; 745 m; 20 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW231; dredge.

Etymology: The specific name honours André Freiwald (Senckenberg am Meer, Germany), in recognition of a fruitful collaboration in the exploration of the North Atlantic seamounts.

Description: Shell (Figure 6) small (holotype, 4.5 × 3.6 mm), solid, consisting of 1 ¹/₄ protoconch and 2 to 2 ³/₄ teleoconch whorls. Protoconch 800 μm in diameter, with a protruding nucleus, without a distinct protoconch I and protoconch II, nearly smooth, with indistinct wrinkles in a spiral direction and very slight folds on the nucleus, parallel to the growth lines. Protoconch/teleoconch discontinuity very sharp, slightly detached from the following whorl. Teleoconch whorls strongly carinate, shouldered, with a moderately deep suture. Sculpture consists of blurry axial ribs and spiral keels. Axial sculpture of about 30 ribs on last whorl, not very prominent, irregular and narrower than the interspaces, fading out abapically, and of distinct axial wrinkles between the ribs and fine growth lines. Spiral sculpture of three strong keels and additional spiral cordlets; one more prominent keel at the upper ³/₄ of the whorls, one

peripheral and one prolonging the suture on the last whorl or situated just above the suture; spiral cordlets 5-8 between keels, 9-14 on the base, indistinct on the adapical shoulder. Umbilicus narrow and deep, sharply delimited by an angulation. Aperture irregularly rounded, slightly angulated by the spiral sculpture. Outer lip thin, simple, receding in its upper half. Parietal edge of aperture thin, appressed to the previous whorl, at an angle with the columellar edge which thickens towards the base. Colour entirely white.

Remarks: This species most resembles the Western Atlantic *H. tubulatum*, with which it has hitherto confused and from which it differs essentially by the nearly smooth protoconch, lacking the quincuncially arranged tubercles of the former species. It differs from *H. hoffmani* n. sp. in having a smaller protoconch with a more protruding nucleus, and in having a distinct axial sculpture and spiral cordlets on the teleoconch.

Haloceras sp. 1 (Fig. 7)

Material examined: HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (2.4 × 2.6 mm); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; Seamount 2 sta. DW200; dredge.

Remarks: One shell from Hyères seamount, Seamount 2 sta. DW200, probably represents an additional undescribed species but is not named because this single specimen is deemed insufficient. The general appearance of the shell is similar to *H. freiwaldi* n. sp.

except for that the axial sculpture consists only of sharp wrinkles parallel to the growth lines, without axial ribs and nodules along the keels. The protoconch is slightly over 1 mm in maximum diameter, compared to 800 μm in *H. freiwaldi*.

Figure 6. *Haloceras freiwaldi* n. sp., from Hyères seamount. A: paratype (MNHN-IM-2000-38806, 2.0 × 2.0 mm), from Seamount 2 sta. DW200 (31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m); B: protoconch of the same paratype, in lateral view; C: apical view of another paratype (MNHN-IM-2000-38806, diameter 2.4 mm), from the same station; D: apical view of another paratype (MNHN-IM-2000-38806, diameter 1.75 mm), same station; E: protoconch, same shell as in D; F: detail of sculpture of first whorl (framed area on D); G-I: Holotype (MNHN-IM-2000-38805, 4.5 × 3.7 mm), from Seamount 2 sta. DW197 (31.314°N, 28.559°W; 1370–1480 m).

Figura 6. *Haloceras freiwaldi* n. sp., del monte submarino Hyères. A: Paratipo (MNHN-IM-2000-38806, 2,0 × 2,0 mm), de la estación Seamount 2 DW200 (31,318°N, 28,600°W; 1060 m); B: protoconcha del mismo paratipo, en vista lateral; C: vista apical de otro paratipo (MNHN-IM-2000-38806, diámetro 2,4 mm), de la misma estación; D: vista apical de otro paratipo (MNHN-IM-2000-38806, diámetro 1,75 mm), de la misma estación; E: protoconcha de la concha en D; F: detalle de la escultura de la primera vuelta (área enmarcada en D); G-I: Holotipo (MNHN-IM-2000-38805, 4,5 × 3,7 mm), de la estación Seamount 2 DW197 (31,314°N, 28,559°W; 1370–1480 m).

Haloceras sp. 2 (Fig. 8)

Material examined: IRVING SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (2.4 × 2.6 mm); 32.143°N, 28.178°W; 1030–1035 m; 28 Jan. 1996; Seamount 2 sta. DW225; dredge.

Figure 7. *Haloceras* sp. 1 from Hyères seamount, Seamount 2 sta. DW200 (31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m). A: shell (2.4 × 2.6 mm) in lateral view. B: same shell in apical view. C: protoconch in lateral view. D: protoconch, in apical view. E: detail of sculpture of first whorl (framed area on B).
 Figura 7. *Haloceras* sp. 1 del monte submarino Hyères, Seamount 2 sta. DW200 (31,318°N, 28,600°W; 1060 m). A: concha (2,4 × 2,6 mm) en vista lateral. B: la misma concha en vista apical. C: protoconcha en vista lateral. D: protoconcha, en vista apical. E: detalle de la escultura de las primeras vueltas (área enmarcada en B).

Remarks: This shell from Irving (Cruiser) seamount, Seamount 2 sta. DW225, probably represents another additional undescribed species. The shell differs from all others of this group found on the southern part of SASC in lacking any definite spiral sculpture and

in having broad axial folds which make an undulated periphery in apical view. The protoconch is also ca. 1 mm in maximum diameter, compared to 800 µm in *H. freiwaldi*, and smooth except for some strong growth lines on its earliest part.

DISCUSSION

The two new species, in addition to *Haloceras meteoricum*, contribute very little change to the overall conclusions of CABALLERO ET AL. (2023) regarding SASC endemism (94 species, 22.9 %; was 92 species, 22.5%) and the amount of species shared with the Western Atlantic (78 species, 19.0%; was 79 species, 19.3%). Contrary to *H. meteoricum*, which belongs to the fauna of the summit of seamounts, the two new species are part of the lower bathyal

species collected mainly below 800 m depth.

Despite the usual great rarity of haloceratids (TAKANO ET AL., 2022), both *H. hoffmani* and *H. freiwaldi* were quite abundant on Hyères seamount, but only two shells of *Haloceras freiwaldi* were found elsewhere, namely on Irving Seamount. Admittedly, Great Meteor seamount was undersampled outside the summit platform, due to the very steep and rough bottom on which the dredge performed

Figure 8. *Haloceras* sp. 2 from Irving seamount, Seamount 2 sta. DW 225 (32.143°N, 28.178°W; 1030–1035 m). A, B: shell (2.4 × 2.6 mm) in lateral and apical view; C: protoconch in apical view.
 Figura 8. *Haloceras* sp. 2 del monte submarino Irving, Seamount 2 sta. DW 225 (32,143°N, 28,178°W; 1030–1035 m). A, B: concha (2,4 × 2,6 mm) en vista lateral y apical; C: protoconcha en vista apical.

poorly, but Irving, Plato and Atlantis seamounts were thoroughly sampled in the same depth interval as Hyères, so that the lack of specimens of these species may be considered significant. The three or five non-planktotrophic *Haloceras* treated in this paper therefore seem to constitute a small local radiation endemic to the southern part of the SASC and have not recorded so far around the Azores.

The shipboard drawing of *Haloceras meteoricum* provides some information on the external morphology of the animal, with some elements supporting the generic placement. The presence of a penis excludes a placement in Cerithioidea or Vermetoidea (PONDER *ET AL.*, 2020: 396). The marked dimple between propodium and metapodium is consistent with the observations by WARÉN & BOUCHET (1993) of “a wide opening between the pro- and mesopodium” in connection with large propodial and metapodial pedal glands. The operculum, noted as present on all live collected species, is also seen in *H. meteoricum*. The cephalic tentacles have quite large eyes embedded at their base, consistently with observations on other species, except that the cephalic tentacles of *H. meteoricum* are cylindrical rather than conical or tapering. WARÉN & BOUCHET (1993) wrote that “presumably no species have a snout” and interpreted the protruding structure between cephalic tentacles as a proboscis, but acknowledged that

it was not clear whether there was a tip of a proboscis or a snout; the same can be said from the drawing of *H. meteoricum*.

It would be tempting to consider a separate genus to accommodate the three (possibly five) non-planktotrophic haloceratids found on the North Atlantic seamounts, and the related Western Atlantic *H. tubulatum*. However, too little is known regarding the phylogeny of the family Haloceratidae, some of which resemble the SASC species in general shell outline, whereas others (including the type species of *Haloceras*) with a discoidal profile and a spiral sculpture on protoconch I could represent one or more distinct lineage. In addition, the loss of planktotrophy is known to occur repeatedly within diverse caenogastropod groups usually featuring planktotrophic larval development (e. g. Conoidea: BOUCHET, 1990, DUDA & PALUMBI, 1999, GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.*, 2018; Turritellidae: LIEBERMANN *ET AL.*, 1993; Littorinidae: REID *ET AL.*, 1996; Calyptraeidae: COLLIN, 2004; Nassariidae: YANG *ET AL.*, 2021; Rissooidea: SLEURS, 2022) and is not *per se* an acceptable character change for supporting a genus-level separation. The impression that *H. japonicum* (at least, the offspring brooded in the Oregon specimen described by WARÉN & BOUCHET, 1993) shares the unusual character of quincuncially arranged knobs on the protoconch

with *H. meteoricum* falls short of supporting a close phylogenetic relationship of both species. Therefore, a conservative placement of the Atlantic species in *Haloceras* is maintained for the time being.

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